

1 **An Archaeological Perspective Towards Maritime Interaction and Mobility**

2 **Alfred F. Pawlik^{1,2}**

3

4 1) Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Ateneo de Manila University, Ricardo and Dr. Rosita Leong Hall, Loyola
5 Heights, Quezon City 1108, Philippines

6 2) TRACES ASIA, Areté, Ateneo de Manila University, Loyola Heights, Quezon City 1108, Philippines

7 Email: apawlik@ateneo.edu

8

9 Introduction

10 In the Philippines, archaeological research has significantly intensified over the past 20 years and
11 is producing useful insights into the Prehistory of this diverse archipelago that is of relevance for the
12 entire region of Island Southeast Asia (ISEA). While research in the past has often focused on the
13 concepts of migration of technologically advanced and agriculture-oriented groups through the
14 Philippine archipelago and into the Pacific (Solheim 1975, 1992; Bellwood 1997, 2005, 2017; Hung
15 2008, 2019; Hung et al. 2011; Simanjuntak, 2008; Thiel 1987, 1990), there is growing evidence for
16 complex interrelationship of pre-Neolithic societies, technological and ecological diversity, and the
17 increasing adaptation to maritime environments already during the Pleistocene.

18 After archaeologists had long hypothesised an association between the fossil Pleistocene megafauna
19 found throughout the Philippines and early hominins, the recent discovery and excavation of the in
20 situ remains of a *Rhinoceros philippinensis* at the Rizal site in Kalinga, northern Luzon, has confirmed
21 the presence of hominins in the Philippines during the early to middle Pleistocene (Beyer 1947;
22 Koenigswald 1958; Fox and Peralta 1974; Fox 1978; Shutler and Mathisen 1979; Ronquillo 1981;
23 Pawlik 2001; Pawlik and Ronquillo 2003; Dizon and Pawlik 2010; Ingicco et al. 2018). A direct ESR/U-
24 series date of 709,000 ± 68,000 before present (BP) was retrieved from tooth enamel of the
25 rhinoceros, while the deposits below and covering the skeleton were dated through Optically
26 stimulated Luminescence dating (OSL) and Argon-Argon dating (Ar/Ar) to between 1.0 and 0.7 million
27 years BP. The rhinoceros was very likely slaughtered by hominins, as indicated by cut marks on
28 several bones, while others were broken up for the purpose of obtaining bone marrow. This evidence
29 was further substantiated by a lithic artefact assemblage recovered from the same context (Ingicco
30 et al. 2018, 2021). The relatively small flakes, less than 100 mm in length, were mainly manufactured
31 from siliceous rocks, such as chert, flint, or quartzite, as well as sedimentary and igneous rocks and
32 remained mostly without further modification. Microscopic use-wear analysis indicated that some
33 may have been used in connection with the butchering of the Rhino but also other uses, e.g. on plant
34 material have been identified (Pawlik 2021a). Among the lithic artefacts were several cores as well as
35 hammerstones, suggesting that tool production occurred at or near the Rhinoceros site. Despite
36 indications that anvil technique was applied on some cores and flakes no anvils have been found at
37 the site or reported from northern Luzon.

38 Presently undated but presumably similarly old is a lithic assemblage that was reported from
39 Arubo in Gen. Tinio, Nueva Ecija, c. 300km south of Kalinga. It contains several larger core tools with
40 unifacial and bifacial modifications, including a handaxe (Pawlik 2001, 2004; Dizon and Pawlik 2010).
41 The artefacts have an unusually formal morphology and are rather untypical for Philippine lithic
42 industries, but appear similar to those from early Palaeolithic assemblages in the mainland of
43 Southeast and East Asia, such as An Khê, Lampong, Roc Tung, Sao Din, and several sites in the Bose
44 Basin in southern China (Huang 1989; Schick and Dong Zhuan 1993; Yamei et al. 2000; Zeitoun et al
45 2012; Derevianko et al. 2016, Pawlik 2021a, 2021b), as well as Pacitan in Java (Sémah and Sémah 2012),
46 and Mata Menge and Wolo Sege on Flores in Island Southeast Asia (van den Bergh et al. 1996;
47 Morwood et al. 1998; Brumm et al. 2006; Simanjuntak et al. 2010; Figure 1). Although the Rizal and
48 Arubo artefacts differ in size and morphology, similarities have been noted regarding core preparation
49 and reduction, and the lithic raw material used (Pawlik 2004, 2021b; Ingicco et al. 2018, 2021).

50 After these episodes on Luzon Island, no presence of hominins is currently recorded until the
51 onset of Oxygen Isotope Stage 4 (OIS 4), c. 70,000 years ago. However, south of the Philippines, the
52 existence of a currently unidentified hominin in Wallacea was manifested in South Sulawesi where
53 lithic artefacts associated with large mammals including *Stegodon* were recovered in the Walanae
54 Basin, dated to between 200-100,000 BP (van den Bergh et al. 2017), indicating that hominins were
55 very likely present in the region, at least during the transitional period from the middle to the late
56 Pleistocene. A metatarsal and a femur fragment together with several teeth were retrieved from Callao
57 Cave near the Kalinga Rhinoceros site (Détroit et al. 2019). Initially identified as modern human
58 (Mijares et al. 2010), the fossils are now assigned to a pre-modern species, "*Homo luzonensis*". U-
59 series dates on a human tooth and associated faunal remains produced ages of around 50,000 BP, with
60 a single date of a human metatarsal fragment of c. 66,000 BP (Grün 2014; Détroit et al. 2019). No
61 artefacts were found associated with the fossil remains.

62 In Palawan, several caves have provided a combined chronological sequence from the Late
63 Pleistocene onwards until the Holocene. The currently oldest fossil remains of several individuals of an
64 anatomically modern human (AMH) were found together with lithic assemblages in Tabon Cave in
65 Palawan (Fox 1970). A re-investigation of Tabon Cave in 2000 obtained a human tibia and a right
66 mandible fragment that were U-series dated to 47,000 +11/-10,000 BP, and 31,000 +8000/-7000 BP,
67 respectively (Détroit et al. 2004), while the well-known "Tabon Man" skull cap was dated to 16,500 ±
68 2000 BP and somewhat younger than the earlier association made by Robert Fox (Fox 1970; Dizon et
69 al. 2002). Although the very high standard errors of the U-Series dates raise some concerns on their
70 reliability, more recent calibrated radiocarbon-dates of hearth features indicate human occupation of
71 Tabon Caves at least around c. 33-39,000 cal. BP (Choa et al. 2016; Choa 2018, Pawlik, 2021).

72
 73 Figure 1: Map of Southeast Asia with locations mentioned in the text. 1) Mata Menge, Wolo Sege, 2)
 74 Liang Bua, 3) Rizal, Kalinga, 4) Arubo, 5) Roc Tung, An Khê, 6) Lampang, 7) Sao Din, 8) Bose Basin, 9)
 75 Pacitan, 10) Walanae Basin, 11) Callao, Musang, Vito, 12) Tabon, Pilanduk, Duyong, Sa-gung, 13) Ille
 76 Cave, 14) Bubog 1 & 2, Bilat Cave, 15) Niah Caves, 16) Golo Cave. Image reproduced from the GEBCO
 77 world map 2014, www.gebco.net.

78
 79 While Palawan was part of the Sunda landmass that was exposed during low sea levels in the
 80 Pleistocene, east of Huxley's Line, the biogeographic boundary that separates the Sundaic region of
 81 Island Southeast Asia (Sundaland) from its oceanic part ("Wallacea"), the earliest sites that indicate a
 82 Pleistocene human presence are situated in Occidental Mindoro. Like most islands of the Philippines,
 83 Mindoro was never connected to the mainland and could only be reached by sea. At its southern end,
 84 excavations of three sites, Bubog 1 and 2 on Ilin Island in San Jose, and Bilat Cave in Sta. Teresa,
 85 Magsaysay (Figure 2, 3), have provided evidence for a Late Pleistocene occupation and produced a
 86 radiocarbon chronology from the 16th century AD down to at least c. 35,000 cal. BP (Pawlik et al. 2014;
 87 Pawlik and Piper 2019; Pawlik 2021b). The sites are in less than 100km straight distance from the
 88 enlarged Palawan landmass that was exposed during sea level regressions in the Pleistocene and might
 89 have provided a gateway for the movements of AMH from the Sundaic region via Borneo and Palawan
 90 into the Philippine archipelago (Pawlik et al. 2014). The Bubog and Bilat sites in Mindoro, as well as Ille
 91 Cave in northern Palawan have delivered evidence for open sea faring and long-distance movements
 92 of people, as well as the transfer of material and immaterial culture, between the islands and the
 93 mainland of Southeast Asia over the last 35,000 years (Pawlik and Fuentes 2023). This includes open

94 sea fishing, long-distance acquisition of obsidian, and the emergence of a diversity of burial rituals,
95 possibly adopted from the Southeast Asian mainland (Piper et al. 2011; Lara et al. 2013, 2016; Pawlik
96 et al. 2014, 2015, 2019; Neri et al. 2015; Boulanger et al. 2019; Pawlik and Piper 2019; Shipton et al.
97 2019). The traits identified in Mindoro and Palawan predate the ‘Austronesian Diaspora’ and the arrival
98 of early farming populations in the Philippines at around 4500-4000 BP considerably (Bellwood 1997,
99 2005, 2017; Simanjuntak 2008, 2017; Thiel 1987, 1990; Piper 2016; Pawlik and Piper 2019).

100
101 Figure 2: Map of Mindoro and Ilin Island with the locations of Bubog 1 and 2, and Bilat Cave (aerial
102 view photo by R. Fuentes)

103
104 Different subsistence strategies can be observed in Palawan and Mindoro. In the faunal
105 assemblages of Palawan, during the late Pleistocene, the most common animal was deer, while during
106 the Holocene, a forest-adapted pig (*Sus ahoenobarbus*) was mainly hunted (Heng 1988; Piper et al.
107 2011; Ochoa and Piper 2017; Pawlik and Piper 2019). *Sus oliveri*, an endemic pig, is dominant in the
108 faunal remains found in Occidental Mindoro sites, next to Tamaraw (*Bubalus mindorensis*), a small
109 water buffalo endemic to Mindoro, and two deer species, *Rusa mariana* and *Cervus alfredi* (Pawlik &
110 Piper, 2019). In addition to abundant marine resources, these larger mammals, as well as small
111 mammals such as arboreal cloud rats and larger lizards, provided significant terrestrial resources
112 (Reyes et al. 2017). The Bubog 1 site on Ilin Island has so far provided the longest chronology from the
113 late Pleistocene to the end of the middle Holocene in the Philippines. The stratigraphy of the site shows
114 changing coastal environments and transition from mangrove swamp forests before the glacial
115 maximum and, after a hiatus during which the site was apparently uninhabited, again at the beginning
116 of the Holocene around 11,000 BP to shallow estuarine and finally open lagoonal habitats around 6000
117 BP (Pawlik et al. 2014; Pawlik and Piper 2019). The remains of various reef and pelagic fishes were

118 found in all shell midden layers and exclusively pelagic fish remains were found in the underlying earlier
119 deposits, dated to c. 33,000 BP ago and earlier (Boulanger 2015; Boulanger et al. 2019, 2023a, b). They
120 include large predatorial species such as Requiem sharks, mackerels, tunas, and bonitos, further
121 indicating the nautical capacity and developed maritime technology of these early seafarers and fishers
122 already before the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM). Among the marine fauna, the discovery of pufferfish
123 (Diodontidae) spines and other skeletal remains at the Mindoro sites is particularly noteworthy. Their
124 minimum number of individuals (MNI) of 154 clearly indicates that this highly toxic fish was not an
125 accidental bycatch, but rather, was deliberately caught. Its poisonous substance, Tetrodotoxin (TTX),
126 was likely extracted and used for hunting, and would have been particularly useful for the small
127 mammals and reptiles found in the faunal assemblages of Bubog 1 and 2, and Bilat Cave (Boulanger et
128 al. 2023b).

129
130 Figure 3: View of A) Bubog 1, B) Bubog 2, and C) Bilat Cave

131
132 Material Culture

133
134 Only few lithic assemblages can be assigned to an early Palaeolithic. Apart from the Kalinga
135 artefacts, a small assemblage of stone tools was retrieved from the open site of Arubo in General Tinio,
136 Nueva Ecija in Central Luzon (Pawlik 2001, 2004; Pawlik and Ronquillo 2003; Teodosio 2005). Among
137 the artefacts were bifacial tools such as a handaxe and a cleaver (Figure 4A, B), as well as unifacially

138 modified artefacts. Several cores revealed the use of different reduction techniques, including a core
139 on a flake in which the ventral face was used as striking platform (Figure 4C). Another core (Figure 4D)
140 shows marked similarities to so-called “horse-hoof” cores found in Sangiran, Java (Koenigswald 1936).
141 While simple choppers and chopping tools also appear in the assemblage (e.g. Figure 4E), several other
142 thoroughly modified artefacts were found at Arubo, such as a unilaterally retouched flake with a partial
143 retouch of its ventral face (Figure 4F), a trapezoidal scraper (Figure 4G), a large and thick flake of which
144 the end was reduced by retouching to a thin and narrow spatula-like tip (Figure 4H), or an elongated,
145 blade-like flake (Figure 4I). Although the site remains undated, the morphological similarity of the
146 bifacial and unifacial tools and the cores from Arubo to early Palaeolithic artefacts from sites in
147 mainland and Island Southeast Asia, including the Kalinga Rhinoceros site, indicates a Middle
148 Pleistocene age (Pawlik 2009, 2021; Ingicco et al. 2018).
149

150
151

Figure 4: Lithic artefacts from Arubo 1 (after Pawlik 2004, Teodosio 2005)

152 Despite a rather early fossil appearance of *Homo sapiens* in Island Southeast Asia, only a few
153 lithic assemblages belonging to the Late Pleistocene have been retrieved in the Philippines. The oldest
154 absolute-dated lithic assemblage ('Flake Assemblage IV') is reported from Tabon Cave in Central
155 Palawan with an associated radiocarbon date of 37-32,000 cal. BP, while the undated 'Flake
156 Assemblage V' found in a lower stratum was estimated through 'age–depth' relationships to have an
157 age of c. 50-45,000 BP, or even earlier (Fox 1970). In general, there is limited apparent production of
158 formal stone tools until the Late Holocene (Patole-Edoumba 2002, 2009; Pawlik and Ronquillo 2003;
159 Pawlik 2010, 2012, 2021; Patole-Edoumba et al. 2012; Pawlik et al. 2014; Fuentes 2019). Several
160 authors have argued that the simplicity of Southeast Asia's lithic industries and the paucity of
161 retouched tools were caused by the scarcity of lithic raw materials of sufficient quality, and the
162 alternative use of abundant organic raw materials like bamboo and wood (Narr 1966; Solheim 1970;
163 Hutterer 1977; White 1977; Pope 1989; Schick and Zhuan 1993; Forestier 2000, 2003; Dennell 2009;
164 Xhaufclair 2014; Xhaufclair et al. 2016). On the other hand, artefacts made of lithic materials that possess
165 a satisfactory knapping quality, including flint, jasper or even obsidian are not uncommon (e.g. Beyer
166 1947; Fox 1970; Charoenwongsa 1988; Pawlik 2004, 2010; Moore and Brumm 2007; Moore et al. 2009;
167 Ono et al. 2010, 2021; Neri et al. 2015; Fuentes et al. 2019; Pawlik and Piper, 2019; Xhaufclair et al.
168 2020), and long-distance exchange systems existed for obsidian probably since the Late Pleistocene
169 (Reepmeyer et al. 2011; Neri et al. 2015; Pawlik 2021b). Bamboo, wood, and other plants were
170 certainly important parts of the prehistoric technologies of ISEA, and this is supported by several use-
171 wear and residue analyses, however, tools made of these materials, if ever, were more likely an
172 addition to the lithic toolkit instead of a replacement, like the few bone tools found in the region
173 (Barton et al. 2009; Pawlik 2010, 2012; Xhaufclair 2014; Barton 2016; Xhaufclair et al. 2016, 2017, 2023;
174 Fuentes et al. 2019, 2020; Ono et al. 2021; Pawlik and Fuentes 2023).

175 Although the number of Pleistocene artefacts made of bone in Southeast Asia is relatively small,
176 it has been suggested that bone technologies arrived with some of the first modern human populations
177 to reach Southeast Asia and were carried by them into the Wallacean part of Island Southeast Asia
178 (Anderson 1990, 1997; Olsen and Glover 2004; Barton et al., 2009; Rabett and Piper 2012; Piper and
179 Rabett, 2014; O'Connor et al. 2014; Pawlik and Piper 2019; Ono et al. 2021). In the Philippines, there
180 is limited evidence for bone technology in the Late Pleistocene and Early Holocene. Notable is a bone
181 fishing gorge from Bubog 1, recovered from deposits below its lowest shell midden layer which was
182 dated to between 33-28,000 cal. BP, and was possibly part of the technology used for open sea bait
183 fishing (Pawlik et al. 2014; Boulanger 2015; Boulanger et al. 2019, 2023a; Pawlik and Piper 2019).
184 Together with the base of a hafted point from Matja Kuru 2 in East Timor, dating to c. 34,000 cal. BP,
185 this is currently the earliest evidence of bone technology east of the Huxley Line (O'Connor et al. 2014;
186 Pawlik and Piper 2019).

187 Shell likely played an equally important role to bone in Late Pleistocene technology. Tools
188 made of shells have been found in sites across ISEA and were often interpreted as scraper-like
189 implements (Willems 1939; van Heekeren 1972; Bronson and Glover 1984; Glover 1986; Arifin 2004;
190 Simanjuntak and Asikin 2004; Bulbeck 2004; Morwood et al. 2007). At Bubog 1, an assemblage of
191 modified flaked and fragmented shell artefacts was retrieved from its lowest shell midden layer,
192 composed of numerous valves of the bivalve *Geloina coaxans*. Two shell tools were directly AMS
193 radiocarbon-dated to 31-28,000 cal. BP, while associated *Conus* and *Strombus* shells produced dates
194 between 33-31,000 cal. BP (Pawlik and Piper 2019). The use of *Tridacnidae* or giant clams for tool
195 making is archaeologically evident in ISEA since the Early Holocene. While flaked artefacts have been
196 occasionally observed, for instance in both Bubog sites on Ilin Island, hafted edge-ground shell adzes
197 appear as the more common tool form (Fox 1970; Glover 1986; Spriggs 1989, 1997; Bellwood 1997;
198 Bellwood et al. 1998; Szabó & Summerhayes 2002; Szabó 2005; O'Connor et al. 2006). In Mindoro, two
199 *Tridacna* adzes from Bilat Cave and Bubog 1 on Ilin Island were directly dated to between 77500-7300
200 cal. BP (Pawlik et al. 2015; Pawlik and Piper 2019; Figure 5A, B). The find of a *Tridacna* adze preform
201 from Bubog 2 on Ilin Island, as well from well-stratified contexts and directly AMS-dated to c. 9000 cal.
202 BP (Figure 5C) suggests that a local production of large *Tridacna* tools already existed in the Philippines
203 during the Early Holocene (Pawlik and Piper 2019; Pawlik 2021b). Intensive wear traces confirmed that
204 it was used as a tool for heavy-duty activities (Pawlik and Piper 2019).

205
206 Figure 5: Shell adzes from Mindoro. A: Bubog 1, B: Bilat Cave, C: Preform from Bubog 2 (after Pawlik et
207 al. 2015; Pawlik and Piper 2019)

208 Use-wear analyses employing low and high power microscopy have identified the use of mostly
209 unretouched flakes on a variety of different materials such as bone, wood, rattan, bamboo, and as
210 implements for hunting gear. Those studies have also demonstrated the usefulness of seemingly
211 simple flakes for various working processes and activities, as well as the application of advanced
212 technologies, such as composite tools and resinous adhesives (Pawlik 2002, 2004, 2006, 2012;
213 Davenport 2003; Teodosio 2005; Xhaufclair and Pawlik 2010; Xhaufclair 2014; Xhaufclair et al. 2016, 2017,
214 2020; Fuentes 2015; Fuentes et al. 2019, 2020, 2021; Fuentes and Pawlik 2020, 2023). At Bubog 1 and
215 2, unmodified igneous beach pebbles were utilized in several ways, but mainly as hammers to open
216 the larger marine shells like *Strombus*, *Trochus* and *Lambis* for consumption, indicated by the
217 diagnostic pitted surfaces that were caused by recurring blows (Pawlik et al. 2014; Pawlik and Piper
218 2019). Some of the hammerstones were later reused as weights for fishing nets or traps (Skakun et al.
219 2014; Boulanger 2015; Boulanger et al. 2019; Pawlik and Piper 2019), while use-wear traces on several
220 hammerstone fragments with sharp edges indicated that they were not discarded once broken but
221 used as tools for the working of harder organic materials (Fuentes and Pawlik 2020). These cases
222 illustrate an efficient use of available resources, but also the importance of traceological analysis in
223 evaluating seemingly simple lithic assemblages rather than just looking at them from a technological
224 perspective. While none of the few bone tools reported from the Philippines have been subjected to
225 traceological analysis so far, use-wear studies have been conducted on the Bubog shell adzes and adze
226 preform made from giant clam, showing that they were used for heavy-duty activities (Pawlik et al.
227 2015). Another use-wear analysis on flaked shell tools produced from the mangrove shell *Geloina*
228 *coaxans* found in the lowest shell midden layer of Bubog 1 and AMS-dated to 28-33,000 BP,
229 determined that they were used for the processing of hard and soft materials (Benz 2016; Pawlik and
230 Piper 2019), similar to 30,000 years old limpet shells from Golo Cave on Gebe Island in North Maluku
231 (Szabó and Koppel 2015). The artefacts from Bubog and Golo not only date the manufacture and
232 utilization of shell tools back to before the LGM, but also demonstrate their versatility for various
233 purposes.

234

235 Synthesis

236

237 The timeline of the arrival of early humans in the Philippines, the colonization of this vast
238 archipelago, and the nature of mobility, technology and maritime interaction between the mainland
239 and the islands of Southeast Asia are major issues in contemporary research in Philippine Archaeology.
240 Early long-distance movements and open water crossings in Island Southeast Asia by modern humans
241 by 50,000 BP or even earlier are evident in the colonization of Sulawesi and Sahul (Clarkson et al. 2017;
242 Westaway et al. 2017; Ono et al. 2020, 2023; Oktaviana et al. 2024). Even earlier movements into

243 Wallacea by archaic hominins during the early-mid Pleistocene are manifested by the presence of
244 stone tools and fossils that were retrieved from several sites in the Soa Basin on Flores Island. Artefacts
245 from Wolo Sege indicated that early hominins were capable of reaching the Wallacean islands already
246 during the final stages of the Early Pleistocene and between 1.0 and 0.8ma BP (Brumm et al. 2006),
247 while a mandible fragment and six isolated teeth belonging to at least three small-jawed and small-
248 toothed individuals retrieved from Mata Menge date to about 0.7ma BP and were reported as similar
249 in dimensions and morphological characteristics to those of *Homo floresiensis* from Liang Bua on the
250 same island (van den Bergh et al. 1996, 2009, 2016).

251 The archaeological record of the Philippines from the Pleistocene until the end of the Mid-
252 Holocene is still fragmentary, and most research has focused only on certain areas of Palawan, Luzon
253 and, more recently, Mindoro, while major parts of this diverse archipelago remain largely unexplored
254 as of today. Furthermore, almost all archaeological materials have been acquired from caves and
255 rockshelters, while no open sites are currently known from this period. It can be assumed that most of
256 the coastal sites near shores and along the coast are now submerged due to rising sea level after the
257 last glacial period.

258 Nevertheless, the archipelago's proximity to Borneo, Sulawesi and Taiwan provided a strategic
259 position to facilitate movements of people, material culture, technologies and innovations across
260 Mainland and Island Southeast Asia. This connectivity between populations over long distances
261 enabled the dissemination of information and ideas along a widespread maritime network was
262 established and utilized long before the arrival of early farming populations in the Late Holocene.
263 During the Late Pleistocene and Early Holocene, the Philippine archipelago was inhabited by hunter-
264 gatherer groups that were well adapted to various inland and coastal environments and capable of
265 responding to changing climates. Developed toolkits included implements made of chert, obsidian,
266 igneous rocks, bone, and shell, that were employed in a diversity of functions and activities. Together
267 with evidence for a long-distance acquisition of raw material, this puts the cliché of a simple and
268 unchanging technology that has been repeatedly brought forward for the prehistory of this region into
269 question. The bearers of these technologies not only used the available materials for every conceivable
270 purpose, but also had the nautical skills to exploit the marine fauna of the open sea and reach remote
271 islands and coasts. By the end of the Pleistocene, they had already established maritime networks
272 across Sunda and Wallacea, sharing material culture and knowledge with various communities living
273 in the region. The successful adaptation to coastal and marine environments and the efficient use of
274 its diverse resources probably ensured a rather successful subsistence strategy for those early
275 islanders, perhaps even in the sense of Sahlins' (1972) concept of the original affluent society.

276

277

278 References

279

280 Anderson D (1990) *Lang Rongrien, a Pleistocene rockshelter: A Pleistocene-Early Holocene*
281 *archaeological site from Krabi, Southwestern Thailand*. Philadelphia: The University Monograph
282 Museum 71.

283 Anderson D (1997) Cave archaeology in Southeast Asia. *Geoarchaeology* 12: 607-638.

284 Barton H (2016) Functional Analysis of Stone Tools from the West Mouth. In Barker G, Farr L (eds)
285 *Archaeological investigations in the Niah Caves, Sarawak. The Archaeology of Niah Caves,*
286 *Sarawak*, Volume 2. McDonald Institute Monographs. McDonald Institute of Archaeological
287 Research, Cambridge.

288 Barton H, Piper PJ, Rabett R, Reeds I (2009) Composite hunting technologies from the Terminal
289 Pleistocene and Early Holocene, Niah Cave, Borneo. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 36:1708–
290 1714.

291 Bellwood P (1997) *Prehistory of the Indo-Malaysian archipelago*. Canberra: Australian National
292 University Press.

293 Bellwood P (2005) *First Farmers: The Origins of Agricultural Societies*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.

294 Bellwood P (2017) *First Islanders: Prehistory of Human Migration in Island Southeast Asia*, New York:
295 John Wiley and Sons.

296 Bellwood P, Nitihaminoto G, Irwin G, Gunadi, Waluyo A, Tanudirjo D (1998) 35,000 Years of Prehistory
297 in the Northern Moluccas, In G.J. Bartstra (ed) *Bird's Head approaches* (Modern Quaternary
298 Research in Southeast Asia 15), pp. 233-275. Rotterdam: Balkema.

299 Benz A (2016) Shell Tool Technology in Southeast Asia. Considerations on Function and Significance
300 of Early Holocene Geloina Artefacts from Bubog 1, Mindoro Occidental, Philippines. Bachelor of
301 Arts thesis, University of Bonn.

302 Beyer HO (1947) Outline Review of Philippine Archaeology by Islands and Province. *Philippine Journal*
303 *of Science* 77: 3-4.

304 Boulanger C (2015) *Etude des comportements de subsistance d'un site australo-mélanésien: Bubog I*
305 *(île d'Ilin, Mindoro, Philippines) ca. 11000-4000 ans BP. Ichtyofaune, crustacés décapodes et*
306 *grands mammifères*. Master's Dissertation. Paris: Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle.

307 Boulanger C, Ingicco T, Piper PJ, Amano N, Grouard S, Ono R, Hawkins S, Pawlik A (2019) Coastal
308 subsistence strategies and mangrove swamp evolution at Bubog I rockshelter (Ilin Island,
309 Mindoro, Philippines) from the Late Pleistocene to the mid-Holocene. *Journal of Island & Coastal*
310 *Archaeology* 14(4): 584-604.

311 Boulanger C, Ingicco T, Sémah A, Hawkins S, Ono R, Reyes M, Pawlik A (2023a) 30,000 years of fishing
312 in the Philippines: New ichthyoarchaeological investigations in Occidental Mindoro. *Journal of*
313 *Archaeological Science: Reports*: 104222.

314 Boulanger C, Pawlik A, O'Connor S, Sémah A, Reyes M, Ingicco T (2023b) The exploitation of toxic fish
315 from the terminal Pleistocene in Island Southeast Asia: the case study of the Mindoro
316 archaeological sites, Philippines. *Animals*, 13, 2113: 1-19.

317 Brumm A, Aziz F, van den Bergh G, Morwood M, Moore M, Kurniawan I, Hobbs D, Fullagar R (2006)
318 Early stone technology on Flores and its implications for Homo floresiensis. *Nature* 441(1): 624-
319 628.

320 Bulbeck D (2004) Divided in space, united in time: The Holocene prehistory of South Sulawesi. In
321 Pasveer JM, Keates S (eds) *Quaternary Research in Indonesia*: 129-66. A.A. Balkema, Leiden.

- 322 Choa O (2018) A geochemical history of Tabon Cave (Palawan, Philippines). Environment, climate,
323 and early modern humans in the Philippine archipelago. PhD thesis, Muséum national d'histoire
324 naturelle, Paris.
- 325 Choa O, Lebon M, Gallet X, Détroit F, Sémah F, et al (2016) Stable isotopes in guano: Potential
326 contributions towards palaeoenvironmental reconstruction in Tabon Cave, Palawan, Philippines.
327 *Quaternary International* 416: 27-37.
- 328 Clarkson C, Jacobs Z, Marwick B, Fullagar R, Wallis L, Smith M, Pardoe C, et al (2017) Human
329 occupation of northern Australia by 65,000 years ago. *Nature* 547, pp.306–310.
- 330 Davenport DR (2003) A Functional Analysis of Southeast Asian - Pacific Island Flaked Stone Tools. BA
331 hon. thesis, Australian National University, Canberra.
- 332 Dennell RW (2009) *The Palaeolithic Settlement of Asia*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- 333 Derevianko A, Su NK, Tsyvbankov A, and Doi NG (2016) *The origin of bifacial industry in Southeast*
334 *Asia*. Novosibirsk: IAET SB RAS Publishing.
- 335 Détroit F, Dizon E, Falgueres C, Hameau S, Ronquillo W, Sémah F (2004) Upper Pleistocene *Homo*
336 *sapiens* from the Tabon cave (Palawan, The Philippines): description and dating of new
337 discoveries. *C.R. Palevol* 3: 705-712.
- 338 Détroit F, Mijares, A, Corny J, Daver G, Zanolli C, Piper, P., et al. (2019) A new species of Homo from
339 the Late Pleistocene of the Philippines. *Nature* 568, 181-186.
- 340 Dizon EZ, Pawlik A (2010) The Lower Palaeolithic Record in the Philippines. *Quaternary International*,
341 223-224: 444–450.
- 342 Forestier H (2000) De quelques chaînes opératoires en Asie du Sud-Est au Pléistocène supérieur final
343 et au début de l'Holocène. *L'Anthropologie* 104: 531-548.
- 344 Forestier H (2003) Des outils nés de la forêt. De l'importance du végétal en Asie du Sud- Est dans
345 l'imagination et l'invention technique aux périodes préhistoriques. In: Froment A, GuffroyJ (eds)
346 *Peuplements anciens et actuels des forêts tropicales : actes du séminaire-atelier*, pp. 315-337.
347 IRD Editions, Paris.
- 348 Fox RB (1970) *The Tabon Caves*. National Museum of the Philippines, Manila.
- 349 Fox RB (1978) The Philippine Paleolithic. In: F. Ikawa-Smith (ed.), *Early Paleolithic in South and East*
350 *Asia*, pp. 59-85. Paris: Mouton.
- 351 Fox RB, Peralta T (1974) Preliminary report on the Paleolithic Archaeology of Cagayan Valley,
352 Philippines, and the Cabalwanian Industry. *Proceedings of the First Regional Seminar on*
353 *Southeast Asian Prehistoric Archaeology*, June 26-July 4, 1972, pp. 100-147. Manila: National
354 Museum.
- 355 Fuentes RB (2015) Use-Wear Analysis of Lithic Artefacts from Vito Cave in Peñablanca, Cagayan,
356 Northern Luzon, Philippines. Master's thesis, University of the Philippines Archaeological Studies
357 Program. Diliman, Quezon City.
- 358 Fuentes R (2019) Detecting microscopic aspects of Late Pleistocene to Early/Mid Holocene lithic
359 technology in Island Southeast Asia: Perspectives from North and Central Sulawesi. PhD
360 Dissertation, Dept. of Prehistory and Quaternary Ecology, University of Tübingen.
361 <http://hdl.handle.net/10900/99029>
- 362 Fuentes R, Pawlik A (2020) Not formal but functional: Traceology and the Lithic Record in the
363 Philippines. In Gibaja-Bao J (ed.), *Hunter-Gatherers tool kit: a functional perspective*, pp. 290-
364 308. Newcastle upon Pyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- 365 Fuentes R, Pawlik A (2022) Barely scratched the surface: development and future directions of lithic
366 use-wear analysis in Island Southeast Asia. *Archaeological Research in Asia*, 33: 100413.

- 367 Fuentes R, Ono R, Nakajima N, Nishizawa H, Siswanto J, Aziz N, Sriwigati, Sofian H, Miranda T, Pawlik
368 A (2019) Technological and behavioural complexity in expedient industries: The importance of
369 use-wear analysis for understanding flake assemblages. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 112:
370 105031.
- 371 Fuentes R, Ono R, Carlos J, Kerfant C, Miranda T, Aziz N, Sriwigati, Sofian H, Pawlik A (2020) Stuck
372 within notches: direct evidence of plant processing during the Last Glacial Maximum to
373 Holocene in North Sulawesi. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 30: 102207.
- 374 Glover IC (1986) *Archaeology in eastern Timor, 1966–67*. Terra Australia 11. Australian National
375 University Press, Canberra.
- 376 Grün R, Eggins S, Kinsley L, Moseley H, Sambridge M (2014) Laser ablation U-series analysis of fossil
377 bones and teeth. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 16: 150-167.
- 378 Hardy J, Hardy S (1969) Ecology of *Tridacna* in Palau. *Pacific Science* 23: 467–72.
- 379 Huang W (1989) Bifaces in China. *Human Evolution* 4(1): 87-92.
- 380 Hung, HC (2008) Migration and cultural interaction in Southern Coastal China, Taiwan and the
381 Northern Philippines, 3000 BC to AD 100: The early history of the Austronesian-speaking
382 populations. PhD thesis, Australian National University, Canberra.
- 383 Hung HC, Carson M, Bellwood P, Campos F, Piper P, Dizon E, Bolunia M, Oxenham M, Zhang C (2011)
384 The first settlement of Remote Oceania: the Philippines to the Marianas. *Antiquity* 85: 909-26.
- 385 Hung, HC (2019) History and Current Debates of Archaeology in Island Southeast Asia. In: C. Smith
386 (ed.), *Encyclopedia of Global Archaeology*, pp. 1-22. Springer Nature.
- 387 Hutterer KL (1977) Reinterpreting the Southeast Asian Paleolithic. In Allen J, Golson J, Jones R (eds.)
388 *Sunda and Sahul, Melanesia and Australia*: 31-71. Academic Press, New York.
- 389 Ingicco T, van den Bergh G, Jago-on C, Bahain JJ, Chacón MG, Amano N, et al. 2018 “Earliest known
390 hominin activity in the Philippines by 709 thousand years ago.” *Nature* 557: 233–37.
- 391 Ingicco T, Reyes MC, de Vos, J, Belarmino M, Albers P, van den Bergh GD, et al. (2020) Taphonomy
392 and chronosequence of the 709 ka Kalinga site formation (Luzon Island, Philippines). *Scientific*
393 *Reports* 10:11081.
- 394 Ingicco T, Sémah F, Zhou Y, Sémah AM, Forestier H. The early lithic productions of Island Southeast
395 Asia: Traditions or convergences? *L'anthropologie* 126(1):102997.
- 396 Ingicco T, Chacon G, Forestier H, Pawlik, A, et al. (in prep) The lithic artefacts from the 709 ka old
397 butchery site of Kalinga (Luzon Island, Philippines). *Journal of Human Evolution*, in prep.
- 398 Koenigswald GHR von (1958) Preliminary report on a newly discovered Stone Age culture from
399 northern Luzon, Philippine Islands. *Asian Perspectives* 2: 69–70.
- 400 Lara M, Lewis H, Paz V, Solheim WG (2013) Bone modification in an Early Holocene cremation burial
401 from Palawan, Philippines. *International Journal of Osteoarchaeology* 5(5): 637–652.
- 402 Lara M, Lewis H, Paz V, Ronquillo W (2016) Implications of pathological changes in cremated human
403 remains from Palawan, Philippines, for island Southeast Asian archaeology. In Oxenham M,
404 Buckley HR (eds) *The Routledge Handbook of Bioarchaeology in Southeast Asia and the Pacific*
405 *Islands*, pp. 339-359. Routledge, London.
- 406 Mijares A, Détroit F, Piper P, Grün R, Bellwood P, Aubert M, Champion G, Cuevas N, De Leon A, Dizon
407 E (2010) New evidence for a 67,000-year-old human presence at Callao Cave, Luzon, Philippines.
408 *Journal of Human Evolution* 59: 123-132.
- 409 Moore MW, Brumm A (2007) Stone artifacts and hominins in island Southeast Asia: new insights from
410 Flores, Eastern Indonesia. *Journal of Human Evolution* 52: 85–102.

- 411 Moore MW, Sutikna T, Jatmiko, Morwood M, Brumm, A (2009) Continuities in stone flaking
412 technology at Liang Bua, Flores, Indonesia. *Journal of Human Evolution* 57: 503–526.
- 413 Morwood M, O’Sullivan P, Aziz F, Raza A (1998) Fission-track ages of stone tools and fossils on the
414 east Indonesian island of Flores. *Nature* 392: 173-76.
- 415 Morwood ML, Sutikna T, Saptomo EW, Westaway KE, Jatmiko, Awe Due R, Moore MW, Dwi Yani
416 Yuniawati, Hadi P, Zhao JX, Turney CSM, Fifield K, Allen H, Soejono RP (2008) Climate, people
417 and faunal succession on Java, Indonesia: evidence from Song Gupuh. *Journal of Archaeological
418 Science* 35: 1776-1789.
- 419 Narr K (1966) *Die frühe und mittlere Altsteinzeit Süd-und Ostasiens. Handbuch für Urgeschichte.*
420 Francke, Munich.
- 421 Neri L, Pawlik A, Reepmeyer C, Mijares A, Paz V (2015) Mobility of Early Islanders in the Philippines
422 during the Terminal Pleistocene/Early Holocene Boundary: PXRf-Analysis of Obsidian Artefacts.
423 *Journal of Archaeological Science* 61: 149-157.
- 424 O’Connor S, Robertson G, Aplin K (2014) Are osseous artefacts a window on perishable material
425 culture? Implications of an unusually complex bone tool from the late Pleistocene of East Timor.
426 *Journal of Human Evolution* 67: 108-119.
- 427 Oktaviana AA, Joannes-Boyau R, Hakim B, Brumm A, Aubert M, et al (2024). Narrative cave art in
428 Indonesia by 51,200 years ago. *Nature*, DOI 10.1038/s41586-024-07541-7.
- 429 Olsen SL, Glover IC (2004) The bone industry of Ulu Leang 1 and Leang Burung 1 rockshelters,
430 Sulawesi, Indonesia, in its regional context. *Modern Quaternary Research in Southeast Asia* 18:
431 273-299.
- 432 Ono R, Soegondho S, Yoneda M (2010) Changing marine exploitation during Late Pleistocene in
433 northern Wallacea: Shell remains from Leang Sarru Rockshelter in Talaud Islands. *Asian
434 Perspectives* 48 (2): 318-341.
- 435 Ono R, Fuentes R, Pawlik A, Sofian HO, Sriwigati, Aziz N, Alamsyah N, Kurozumi T, Yoneda M (2021)
436 Island migration and foraging behaviour by anatomically modern humans during the late
437 Pleistocene to Holocene in Wallacea: New evidence from Central Sulawesi, Indonesia.
438 *Quaternary International* 596, 124-143.
- 439 Patole-Edoumba E (2002) L’industrie Lithique Préhistorique de Débitage des Philippines de la Fin du
440 Pleistocène à l’Holocène Moyen. PhD thesis, University of Aix-Marseille I.
- 441 Patole-Edoumba E (2009) A Typo-Technological Definition of Tabonian Industries. *Bulletin of the Indo-
442 Pacific Prehistoric Association* 29: 21–25.
- 443 Patole-Edoumba E, Pawlik, A, Mijares A (2012) Evolution of prehistoric lithic industries of the
444 Philippines during the Pleistocene. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 11(2–3): 213-230.
- 445 Pawlik, A (2001) Is there an Early Palaeolithic in the Philippines? New Approaches for Lithic Analysis
446 in the Philippines. In M Horrocks and P Sheppard (eds), *Australasian Connections and New
447 Directions*. Research Papers in Anthropology and Linguistics, Vol. 5, pp. 255-270. Auckland:
448 University of Auckland.
- 449 Pawlik A (2004) The Palaeolithic Site of Arubo 1 in Central Luzon, Philippines. *Bulletin of the Indo-
450 Pacific Prehistory Association* 24: 3-12.
- 451 Pawlik A (2010) Have we overlooked something? Hafting traces and indications of modern traits in
452 the Philippine Palaeolithic. *Bulletin of the Indo-Pacific Prehistory Association* 30: 35-53.
- 453 Pawlik A (2012) Behavioural Complexity and Modern Traits in the Philippine Upper Palaeolithic. *Asian
454 Perspectives* 51 (1): 22-46.

- 455 Pawlik A (2015) Detecting Traits of Modern Behavior through Microwear Analysis. A Case Study from
 456 the Philippine Terminal Pleistocene. In Kaifu Y, Izuho M, Ono A, Sato H, Goebel T (eds) *Emergence*
 457 *and Diversity of Modern Human Behavior in Palaeolithic Asia*: 182-200. Texas A&M University
 458 Press, Post Station.
- 459 Pawlik A (2021a) Traceological analysis of the stone tools from the Middle Pleistocene Rhinoceros
 460 butchery site of San Pedro in Rizal, Kalinga, Philippines (Preprint). *Zenodo*, DOI
 461 10.5281/zenodo.12660642.
- 462 Pawlik A (2021b) Technology, adaptation, and mobility in maritime environments in the Philippines
 463 from the Late Pleistocene to Early/Mid-Holocene. *Quaternary International* 596, 109–123.
- 464 Pawlik A, Ronquillo W (2003) The Palaeolithic in the Philippines. *Lithic Technology* 28(2): 79-93.
- 465 Pawlik A, Piper, PJ (2019) The Philippines from c. 14,000 – 4,000 cal BP in Regional Context.
 466 *Cambridge Archaeological Journal* 29(1): 1-22.
- 467 Pawlik A, Fuentes R (2023) Prehistoric Hunter-Gatherers in the Philippines -Subsistence strategies,
 468 adaptation, and behaviour in maritime environments. *Frontiers in Earth Sciences* 11:1110147.
 469 DOI 10.3389/feart.2023.1110147.
- 470 Pawlik AF, Piper PJ, Faylona M, Padilla S, Carlos J, Mijares A, Vallejo B, Ingicco T, Reyes MC, Amano
 471 N, Porr, M (2014) Archaeological excavations at Bubog I & II on Ilin Island, Philippines:
 472 Preliminary studies on island adaptation and foraging strategies in changing environments from
 473 the Terminal Pleistocene to the early Holocene. *Journal of Field Archaeology*: 230-247.
- 474 Pawlik A, Piper PJ, Wood R, Lim K, Faylona M, Mijares A, and Porr M (2015) Shell tool technology in
 475 Island Southeast Asia: an early Middle Holocene Tridacna adze from Ilin Island, Mindoro,
 476 Philippines. *Antiquity* 89: 292-308.
- 477 Pawlik A, Crozier R, Fuentes R, Wood R, Piper P (2019) A 5th millennium BP flexed inhumation from
 478 Bubog 1, Ilin Island, Mindoro Occidental, chronologically based in the Holocene burial traditions
 479 of Southeast Asia. *Antiquity* 93: 901-918.
- 480 Piper PJ (2016) Human cultural, technological and adaptive changes from the end of the Pleistocene
 481 to the mid-Holocene in Southeast Asia. In Oxenham M, Buckley HR (eds), *The Routledge*
 482 *Handbook of Bioarchaeology in Southeast Asia and the Pacific Islands*, pp. 24-44. London:
 483 Routledge.
- 484 Piper PJ, Rabett RJ (2014) Late Pleistocene subsistence strategies in Southeast Asia and their
 485 implications for understanding the development of modern human behaviour. In Dennell R, Porr
 486 M (eds) *Southern Asia, Australasia and the search for modern human origins*, pp. 118-134.
 487 Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- 488 Piper PJ, Ochoa J, Robles E, Lewis H, Paz V (2011) Palaeozoology of Palawan Island, Philippines.
 489 *Quaternary International* 233: 142–158.
- 490 Pope GC (1989) Bamboo and Human Evolution. *Natural History* (October):1–15.
- 491 Rabett RJ, Piper PJ (2012) The emergence of bone technologies at the end of the Pleistocene in island
 492 and mainland Southeast Asia and their regional implications. *Cambridge Archaeological Journal*
 493 22(1): 37-56.
- 494 Reepmeyer C, Spriggs M, Anggraeni, Lape P, Neri L, Ronquillo W, Simanjuntak T, Summerhayes G,
 495 Tanudirjo D, Tiauzon A (2011) Obsidian sources and distribution system in Island southeast Asia:
 496 new results and implications from geochemical research using LA-ICPMS. *Journal of*
 497 *Archaeological Science* 38: 2995-3005.
- 498 Reyes, M, Ingicco, T, Piper, P Amano, N, Pawlik, A 2017: First fossil evidence of an extinct cloud rat
 499 (*Crateromys paulus*) (Chordata: Mammalia: Rodentia, Muridae) from Ilin Island, Mindoro

- 500 (Philippines): Insights on *Crateromys paulus* diversity and *Crateromys* systematics. *Proceedings*
501 *of the Biological Society of Washington* 130: 84–97.
- 502 Ronquillo W (1981) The technological and functional analyses of lithic flake tools from Rabel Cave,
503 Northern Luzon, Philippines. Manila: National Museum
- 504 Sahlins M (1972) The Original Affluent Society. In M. Sahlins, *Stone Age Economics*, pp.1-39. Chicago:
505 Aldine Atherton.
- 506 Schick K, Zhuan D (1993) Early Paleolithic of China and Eastern Asia. *Evolutionary Anthropology* 2:
507 22–35.
- 508 Sémah AM, Sémah F (2012) The rainforest in Java through the Quaternary and its relationships with
509 humans (adaptation, exploitation and impact on the forest). *Quaternary International* 249: 120-
510 128.
- 511 Shipton, C, O'Connor S, Reepmeyer C, Kealy S, Jankowski N (2019) Shell Adzes, Exotic Obsidian, and
512 Inter-Island Voyaging in the Early and Middle and Holocene of Wallacea. *Journal of Island and*
513 *Coastal Archaeology*. DOI:10.1080/15564894.2019.1581306.
- 514 Shutler, R, Mathisen, M (1979) 1979 Pleistocene Studies in the Cagayan Valley of Northern Luzon,
515 Philippines. *Journal of the Hong Kong Archaeological Society* 8, 105-114.
- 516 Simanjuntak T (2008) *Austronesian in Sulawesi*. Center for Prehistoric and Austronesian Studies,
517 Depok.
- 518 Simanjuntak T (2017) The Western Route Migration: A Second Probable Neolithic Diffusion to
519 Indonesia. In Piper P, Matsumura H, Bulbeck D (eds) *New Perspectives in Southeast Asian and*
520 *Pacific Prehistory*, pp. 201-211. Terra Australis 45. Canberra: Australian National University
521 Press.
- 522 Simanjuntak T, Asikin, IN (2004) Early Holocene human settlement in eastern Java. *Bulletin of the*
523 *Indo-Pacific Prehistory Association* 24: 13-29.
- 524 Simanjuntak T, Sémah F, Gaillard C (2010) The Palaeolithic in Indonesia: Nature and Chronology.
525 *Quaternary International* 223-224: 418–21.
- 526 Solheim WG II (1970) Prehistoric Archaeology in Eastern Mainland Southeast Asia and the Philippines.
527 *Asian Perspectives* 13: 47–58.
- 528 Solheim WG II (1975) The Nusantara and South China. *Journal of the Hong Kong Archaeological Society*
529 6: 108-115.
- 530 Solheim WG II (1992) Nusantara traders beyond Southeast Asia, in I. C. Glover, P. Suchitta & J. Villiers
531 (eds.), *Early Metallurgy, Trade and Urban Centres in Thailand and Southeast Asia*, pp. 199-212.
532 Bangkok: White Lotus.
- 533 Szabó K (2005) Technique and practice: Shell-working in the western Pacific and Island Southeast
534 Asia. Doctoral thesis. Australian National University, Canberra.
- 535 Szabó K, Summerhayes G (2002) Lapita worked shell artefacts: new data from early Lapita. In Sand C,
536 Bedford S, Burley D (eds) *Fifty Years in the Field: Essays in Honour and Celebration of Richard*
537 *Shutler Jr's Archaeological Career*: 91-100. New Zealand Archaeological Association Monograph
538 25, Auckland.
- 539 Szabó K, Koppel B (2015) Limpet shells as unmodified tools in Pleistocene Southeast Asia: an
540 experimental approach to assessing fracture and modification. *Journal of Archaeological Science*
541 54: 64-75.
- 542 Teodosio S (2005) A Functional Analysis of the Arubo Stone Tools. Master thesis, University of the
543 Philippines Diliman.

- 544 Thiel B (1987) Excavations at the Lal-Lo Shell middens, Northeast Luzon, Philippines. *Asian*
545 *Perspectives* 27(1): 71-94.
- 546 Thiel B (1990) Excavations at Musang Cave, Northeast Luzon, Philippines. *Asian Perspectives* 28: 61-
547 81.
- 548 Van Heekeren HR (1972) *The Stone Age of Indonesia*. Second edition. Martinus Nijhoff, The Hague.
- 549 Van den Bergh G, Mubroto B, Aziz F, Sondaar P, De Vos J (1996) Did Homo erectus reach the Island
550 of Flores? *Bulletin of the Indo-Pacific Prehistory Association* 14: 27-36.
- 551 Van den Bergh G, Bo Li, Brumm A, Grün R, Yurnaldi D, Moore M, Morwood M, et al (2017) Earliest
552 hominin occupation of Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Nature* 529: 208-226.
- 553 Westaway KE, Louys J, Awe RD, Morwood M, Price GJ, Zhao JX, Aubert M, Joannes-Boyau R, Smith
554 TM, Skinner MM, Compton T, Bailey RM, Van den Bergh, GD, De Vos J, Pike A, Stringer C,
555 Saptomo EW, Rizal Y, Zaim J, Santoso WD (2017) An early modern human presence in Sumatra
556 73,000-63,000 years ago. *Nature* 548: 322-325.
- 557 White JP (1977) Crude, colourless and unenterprising? Prehistorians and their views on the stone age
558 of Sunda and Sahul. In Allen J, Golson J, Jones R (eds) *Sunda and Sahul: Prehistoric Studies of*
559 *Southeast Asia, Melanesia and Australia*: 13–30. Academic Press, London.
- 560 Willems W (1939) Merkwaardige praehistorische schelpartefacten van Celebes en Java. *Cultureel*
561 *Indie* 1: 181-185.
- 562 Khaufclair H (2014) Plant use in the subsistence strategies of prehistoric hunter-gatherers in Palawan
563 Island assessed from the lithic industry. PhD thesis, Muséum national d'histoire naturelle, Paris.
- 564 Khaufclair H, Pawlik A (2010) Usewear and Residue Analysis: Contribution to the Study of the Lithic
565 Industry from Tabon Cave, Palawan, Philippines. *Annali dell'Università di Ferrara Museologia*
566 *Scientifica e Naturalistica* 6: 147–54.
- 567 Khaufclair H, Pawlik A, Gaillard C, Forestier H, Vitales TJ, Callado JR, Tandang D, Amano N, Manipon D
568 (2016) Characterisation of the use-wear resulting from bamboo working and its importance to
569 address the hypothesis of the existence of a bamboo industry in prehistoric Southeast Asia.
570 *Quaternary International* 416: 95-125.
- 571 Khaufclair H, Revel A, Vitales TJ, Callado JR, Tandang D, Gaillard C, Forestier H, Dizon E, Pawlik A (2017)
572 What plants might potentially have been used in the forests of prehistoric Southeast Asia? An
573 insight from the resources used nowadays by local communities in the forested highlands of
574 Palawan Island. *Quaternary International* 448: 169-189.
- 575 Khaufclair H, Pawlik A, Jago-on S, Callado JR, Tandang D, Palconit T, Manipon D, Gaillard C,
576 Theodoropoulou A, Forestier H (2020) Plant processing experiments and use-wear analysis of
577 Tabon Cave artefacts question the intentional character of denticulated stone tools in
578 prehistoric Southeast Asia. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 30.
- 579 Khaufclair H, Jago-on S, Manipon D, Amano N, Callado J, Tandang D, Kerfant C, Choa O and Pawlik A
580 (2023) The invisible plant technology of Prehistoric Southeast Asia: Indirect evidence for basket
581 and rope making at Tabon Cave, Philippines, 39-33,000 years ago. *PLoS ONE* 18(6): e0281415.
582 DOI10.1371/journal.pone.0281415.
- 583 Yamei Hou, Potts R, Yuan Baoyin, Guo Zhengtang, Deino A, Wang Wei, Clark A, et al (2000) Mid-
584 Pleistocene Acheulean-like stone technology of the Bose Basin, South China. *Science* 287: 122
- 585 Zeitoun V, Forestier H, Auetrakulvit P, Khaokhiew C, Rasse M, Davtian G, Winayalai C (2012) Discovery
586 of a prehistoric site at Sao Din (Nanoi, Nan province, Northern Thailand): Stone tools and new
587 geological insights. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 11: 575–580.